

DMP Herbicides as tool for selection of edible protein-rich mutants

Version 4

Description

Data management plan for project "Herbicides as tool for selection of edible protein-rich mutants", project No. lzp-2022/1-0126.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Herbicides as tool for selection of edible protein-rich mutants (lzp-2022/1-0126)

Researchers

Ilze Vamža (orcid:0000-0001-8333-0838)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [DMP Herbicides as tool for selection of edible protein-rich mutants](#)

Description:

Data management plan for project "Herbicides as tool for selection of edible protein-rich mutants", project No. lzp-2022/1-0126.

Researchers:

[Ilze Vamža \(orcid:0000-0001-8333-0838\)](#)

Organizations:

[Riga Technical University](#)

Contact: [Kalnbalkite Antra Kalnbalkīte \(antra.kalnbalkite@rtu.lv\)](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [Herbicides as tool for selection of edible protein-rich mutants \(lzp-2022/1-0126\)](#)

Project: [Herbicides as tool for selection of edible protein-rich mutants](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Experimental dataset on mutant generation, amino acid inhibitor-based screening, and process optimization for enhanced protein and essential amino acid production in *Bacillus subtilis*

This dataset contains experimental results from shake-flask and bioreactor cultivation of *Bacillus subtilis* to produce protein-rich biomass. The study includes medium optimisation, mutagenesis, and screening of mutant strains with improved protein synthesis.

The dataset comprises results from media-screening experiments using different carbon and nitrogen sources, as well as Response Surface Methodology (RSM) designs to evaluate the effect of medium composition on biomass yield and protein production. Mutants were generated using EMS treatment, screened in the presence of amino acid inhibitors, and evaluated for performance in shake flasks.

The best-performing mutant and optimised medium were validated in batch fermentation in a 5 L stirred bioreactor under controlled conditions.

The dataset includes biomass concentration, protein content, protein yield, and, where applicable, amino acid composition, along with information on medium composition, cultivation conditions, and process parameters.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection was to develop and evaluate a methodological approach for generating microorganism mutants with enhanced protein and essential amino acid synthesis. The dataset supports the project objective of improving single-cell protein production through a combination of strain improvement and process optimization.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5,2

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

These data can be reused in future research, where additional experiments are conducted under similar or modified cultivation conditions. In such cases, the existing dataset can serve as a baseline for comparison with new experimental results.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

No specific metadata standard is used.

No specific metadata standard was used. The dataset consists of original experimental data from flask and bioreactor cultivation experiments, and metadata are provided in the dataset description and column headers.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The dataset is provided upon request through authentication in Zenodo.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

research.rtu.lv

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The dataset is provided in Microsoft Excel (.xlsx) format and can be easily converted to CSV if needed. These formats are widely supported and can be opened or analysed using open-source tools.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Standard scientific terminology and measurement units are used to describe the dataset variables, facilitating interoperability and reuse.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The dataset will be associated with a scientific publication and deposited in the Zenodo repository.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-04-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The data will remain reusable for the long term, as the dataset is deposited in the Zenodo repository.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Herbicides as tool for selection of edible protein-rich mutants

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Data are stored on institutional computers that are protected by password-based access. Physical access to the computer facilities is restricted to authorised personnel only.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Experimental dataset on biomass, protein, and astaxanthin production by the mutant yeast *Phaffia rhodozyma* AEC3/9 in flask and bioreactor cultivation

This dataset contains experimental results from flask and bioreactor cultivation of the mutant yeast strain *Phaffia rhodozyma* AEC3/9 used for biomass and protein production studies.

The dataset includes results from 31 flask experiments designed using a central composite design to evaluate the effect of medium composition and cultivation parameters on biomass yield, protein content, and astaxanthin accumulation after 7 days of cultivation.

Based on these experiments, an optimized medium was selected and validated in batch fermentation performed in a 5 L stirred bioreactor (4 L working volume) under controlled pH (5.86) and dissolved oxygen (70%) conditions.

The dataset includes experimental results for biomass yield, protein content, astaxanthin content, and bioreactor fermentation kinetics, as well as information on medium composition, cultivation conditions, and operational parameters.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Experimental dataset on biomass, protein, and astaxanthin production by the mutant yeast *Phaffia rhodozyma* AEC3/9 in flask and bioreactor cultivation

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

110

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

These data can be reused in future research, where additional experiments are conducted under similar or modified cultivation conditions. In such cases, the existing dataset can serve as a baseline for comparison with new experimental results.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

No specific metadata standard is used.

No specific metadata standard was used. The dataset consists of original experimental data from flask and bioreactor cultivation experiments, and metadata are provided in the dataset description and column headers.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The dataset is provided upon request through authentication in Zenodo.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

research.rtu.lv

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The dataset is provided in Microsoft Excel (.xlsx) format and can be easily converted to CSV if needed. These formats are widely supported and can be opened or analysed using open-source tools.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Standard scientific terminology and measurement units are used to describe the dataset variables, facilitating interoperability and reuse.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The dataset will be associated with a scientific publication and deposited in the Zenodo repository.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-03-12

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The data will remain reusable for the long term, as the dataset is deposited in the Zenodo repository.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Herbicides as tool for selection of edible protein-rich mutants

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Data are stored on institutional computers that are protected by password-based access. Physical access to the computer facilities is restricted to authorised personnel only.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Experimental dataset on mutant generation, amino acid inhibitor-based screening, and process optimization for enhanced protein and essential amino acid production in *Candida utilis*

This dataset contains experimental results from shake-flask and bioreactor cultivation of *Candida utilis* for the production of protein-rich biomass. The study includes medium optimisation, mutagenesis, and screening of mutant strains with improved protein synthesis.

The dataset comprises results from media screening experiments with different carbon and nitrogen sources, as well as Response Surface Methodology (RSM) designs used to evaluate the effect of medium composition on biomass yield and protein production. Mutants were generated using EMS treatment, screened in the presence of amino acid inhibitors, and evaluated for performance in shake flasks.

The best-performing mutant and optimised medium were validated in batch fermentation in a 5 L stirred bioreactor under controlled conditions.

The dataset includes biomass concentration, protein content, protein yield, and, where applicable, amino acid composition, along with information on medium composition, cultivation conditions, and process parameters.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection was to develop and evaluate a methodological approach for generating microorganism mutants with enhanced protein and essential amino acid synthesis. The dataset supports the project objective of improving single-cell protein production through a combination of strain improvement and process optimisation.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

2

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

These data can be reused in future research, where additional experiments are conducted under similar or modified cultivation conditions. In such cases, the existing dataset can serve as a baseline for comparison with new experimental results.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

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2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

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2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

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2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

research.rtu.lv

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

The dataset is provided in Microsoft Excel (.xlsx) format and can be easily converted to CSV if needed. These formats are widely supported and can be opened or analysed using open-source tools.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Standard scientific terminology and measurement units are used to describe the dataset variables, facilitating interoperability and reuse.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The dataset will be associated with a scientific publication and deposited in the Zenodo repository.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-04-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The data will remain reusable for the long term, as the dataset is deposited in the Zenodo repository.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

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Euro

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Data are stored on institutional computers that are protected by password-based access. Physical access to the computer facilities is restricted to authorised personnel only.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

In search of the best technological solutions for creating edible protein-rich mutants: a multi-criteria analysis approach

Supplementary data to the article " In search of the best technological solutions for creating edible protein-rich mutants: a multi-criteria analysis approach ".

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of collecting and generating the supplementary data for the article "In search of the best technological solutions for creating edible protein-rich mutants: a multi-criteria analysis approach" was to support a transparent, systematic, and reproducible multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) aimed at identifying and comparing technological solutions for producing edible protein-rich mutants.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Aggregate data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

352

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No data re-use.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

Metadata were not added separately because the dataset is provided as supplementary material to a peer-reviewed publication, where its structure, content, and context are fully documented. The data are not published as an independent dataset in a repository, and therefore, no standalone metadata record was created.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

research.rtu.lv

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

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2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

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2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The dataset is associated with a scientific publication.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2024-04-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The data will remain reusable for the long term, as the dataset is deposited in the dspace.emu.ee

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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